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VMS mineral system characterization and deposit model

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Table of content

Table of content	I
List of figures	III
List of tables	IV
1. Introduction	ii
2. Mineral System Types and Test Sites.....	ii
2.1. Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS): Saramäki, Finland (WP2).....	ii
2.2. Fertile Granites and Related Mineralization: Erzgebirge, Germany (WP3)	v
2.3. Alkaline Metasomatic REE–Zr–Mo Systems: Hůrky, Czech Republic (WP4).....	vii
3. Target Elements and Isotope Systems.....	ix
3.1. Sr Isotopes.....	ix
3.1.1. Principles of Sr Isotope System	ix
3.1.2. Mass Spectrometry Techniques	ix
3.1.3. Sample Preparation and Mineral Selection	x
3.1.4. In Situ and Micro-analytical Approaches	x
3.2. Pb Isotopes.....	xi
3.2.1. Principles of Pb Isotope System	xi
3.2.2. Isotopic Fractionation and Mass Bias.....	xi
3.2.3. Sample Preparation.....	xii
3.3. Li Isotopes.....	xiii
3.3.1. Principles of the Lithium Isotope System.....	xiii
3.3.2. Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation	xiv
3.4. Mo Isotopes.....	xiv

3.4.1.	Principles of the Molybdenum Isotope System	xiv
3.4.2.	Analytical Protocols for Molybdenum Isotopes.....	xv
3.4.3.	Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation	xv
3.4.4.	In Situ and Micro-Analytical Approaches.....	xvi
3.5.	Cu Isotopes.....	xvi
3.5.1.	Principles of the Copper Isotope System	xvi
3.5.2.	Analytical Methodologies for Copper Isotopes	xvii
3.5.3.	Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation	xviii
4.	High-Resolution Elemental Analysis Using TQ-ICP-MS.....	xviii
4.1.	Fundamental Architecture	xviii
4.2.	Analytical Protocols for Targeted Isotope System.....	xx
4.2.1.	Strontium (Sr) Isotope Analysis.....	xx
4.2.2.	Lead (Pb) Isotope Analysis.....	xxi
4.2.3.	Other Isotope Systems (Li, Cu, Mo).....	xxii
5.	Preliminary Results of Isotope and Elemental Concentration by using TQ-ICP-MS.....	xxii
5.1.	Analytical Protocols and Sample Preparation for Elemental Concentration and Isotope Measurement by using TQ-ICP-MS	xxii
5.1.1.	Sample Homogenization and Digestion and Protocol for the Trace Elements Analysis by TQ-ICP-MS	xxii
5.1.2.	Post-Digestion Processing and Vessel Maintenance	xxiii
5.1.3.	Clean Laboratory Procedures and Instrumental Analysis	xxiii
5.1.4.	Sample Inventory and Analytical Objectives.....	xxiv
5.2.	Strontium (Sr) Isotope Method Development and Protocol Testing.....	xxviii
5.2.1.	Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation	xxviii

5.2.2.	TQ-ICP-MS Method Optimization	xxx
5.2.3.	Reaction Gas Performance and Matrix Interference	xxxii
5.2.4.	Rb-Doping Tests and Matrix Influence	xxxii
5.2.5.	Standard Reference Materials (SRMs) for Sr Isotopic Analysis.....	xxxii
5.2.6.	Key Components of the Protocol	xxxii
5.3.	Thermo Scientific iCAP TQ ICP-MS Parameters for Strontium Isotope Measurement xxxiii	
5.3.1.	Plasma and Interface Parameters	xxxiii
5.3.2.	Reaction Cell Conditions	xxxiv
5.3.3.	Mass Selection and MS/MS Transitions	xxxiv
5.3.4.	Data Acquisition Settings	xxxiv
6.	Application of Sr Isotope Method Development on Plant Samples for Total Digestion and Sr Separation	xxxv
7.	Conclusions	xxxix
8.	References	xl
	Annex A1: History of Changes of the document.....	xlvi

List of figures

Figure 1 Geological map of the Outokumpu region and location of Outokumpu-type Cu-Zn-Co-Ni deposits and Ni-Co-Cu deposits (Saramäki deposit and Miihkali massif indicated). iv

Figure 2 Geological sketch-map of the Erzgebirge–Vogtland province illustrating the regional distribution of Variscan granitic types, where western and eastern outcropping complexes

contrast with centrally located subsurface bodies like the Markersbach granite (modified from [10]). vi

Figure 3 (a) Schematic regional map displaying the geological terranes of Western and Central Europe. (b) Geographical and tectonic setting of the Čistá-Jesenice Composite Pluton within the Teplá-Barrandian Zone of the Bohemian Massif. (c) Detailed geological sketch map of the Čistá-Jesenice Composite Pluton (from [11]). viii

Figure 4 Schematic diagram of triple quadrupole ICP-MS (TQ-ICP-MS) instrumentation showing the complete ion pathway from sample introduction through detection. The system comprises an inductively coupled plasma (ICP) ion source, interface region with sampler and skimmer cones, ion optics, first quadrupole mass filter (Q1), collision/reaction cell (CRC), second quadrupole mass filter (Q2), and ion detector. xx

Figure 5 ^{87}Sr determination via O_2 mass-shift mode in ICP-QQQ [21]. xxi

Figure 6 Schematic of ^{204}Hg interference removal via TQ-ICP-MS reaction cell NH_3 [80]. xxi

Figure 7 Overview of sample selection and preparation procedures for trace element and isotopic analysis via TQ-ICP-MS. xxiv

Figure 8 Sample preparation and acid digestion process for TQ-ICP-MS analysis. xxv

Figure 9 Sample preparation for Sr separation via ion-exchange chromatography columns. xxvi

Figure 10 Bar chart showing trace element concentrations (ppb) from samples measured by TQ-ICP-MS. xxviii

Figure 11 Dilution factor for selected samples after digestion. xxviii

Figure 12 Bar chart comparing accepted values and corrected of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratio measured by TQ-ICP-MS. xxxiii

List of tables

Table 1 Granite Classifications of the Erzgebirge District vi

Table 2 Summary of sample weights, final dilution weights, and calculated dilution factors. xxvii

Table 3 Ion-exchange chromatography methods for Cu, Mo, and Sr [82]. xxx

Table 4 Summary of analytical run and integration parameters for TQ-ICP-MS protocol testing.
..... xxxi

Table 5 Summary of Standard Reference Materials (SRMs) used for Sr separation and total digestion in the Sr isotope standard-sample bracketing (SSB) protocol. xxxiii

Table 6 Thermo Scientific iCAP TQ ICP-MS parameters for Strontium (Sr) isotope measurement. xxxiv

Table 7 Analytical results of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratios for various geological samples and reference materials measured by TQ-ICP-MS, including a comparison with accepted values and literature data. xxxv

Table 8 Analytical results of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratios for various geological samples, biological materials, and certified reference standards for Sr separation samples measured via TQ-ICP-MS. xxxvii

1. Introduction

The objective of the tasks 2.2, 3.2 and 4.2 is to develop, validate, and document advanced geochemical and isotopic analytical protocols capable of detecting ultra-low concentration signals associated with deep-seated mineral systems using surface-derived media. Within the framework of the DeepBEAT project, this deliverable addresses the need to enhance the sensitivity, precision, and interpretability of surface geochemical data in order to identify distal geochemical footprints of concealed mineralization. The work focuses on improving analytical approaches for complex matrices such as vegetation and till, which are increasingly recognized as valuable archives of geochemical information in covered terrains. By providing standardized, high resolution analytical workflows, this deliverable supports the broader DeepBEAT objective of extending the effectiveness of surface geochemistry for deep mineral exploration while minimizing environmental disturbance.

2. Mineral System Types and Test Sites

2.1. Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS): Saramäki, Finland (WP2)

The Saramäki Cu–Zn prospect is located in eastern Finland, approximately 25 km north-northeast of Outokumpu, at the southern margin of the Miihkali serpentinite massif within the Outokumpu region Figure 1[1,2] . The Miihkali massif forms part of the Outokumpu-type rock assemblage, representing a tectonically emplaced ophiolitic complex composed of mantle-derived ultramafic rocks, associated skarns, metasedimentary units, and structurally controlled sulphide mineralization [7,8]. The massif extends roughly 15 km in a north–south direction and consists predominantly of altered ultramafic lithologies, including serpentinites, talc–carbonate rocks, and metaperidotites, with subordinate metagabbros and chlorite schists [3,7]. Marginal zones of the massif are lithologically heterogeneous and include tremolite-rich skarns, metabasites, quartz-rich rocks, and black schists.

Mineralization at Saramäki occurs within a structurally controlled, shallowly dipping slab of Outokumpu-type lithologies in the southern part of the Miihkali massif, where intense deformation, shearing, and faulting have fragmented the assemblage into discontinuous horizons [2,5,7]. In this area, the mineralized sequence is typically 40–80 m thick and dips 20–25° to the southeast. It is dominated by tremolite skarns, carbonate–tremolite rocks, chlorite schists, quartz-rich rocks, and black schists, while ultramafic rocks are present only as thin and discontinuous lenses [4,7]. According to Kontinen et al. [7], these lithologies reflect extensive metasomatic modification of both ultramafic and sedimentary protoliths during fluid–rock interaction along major shear zones. The strong lithological variability over short drill intervals and the presence of banded and replacement textures are consistent with the metasomatic replacement of mica schists rather than the preservation of primary igneous layering [4,7].

The sulphide mineralization forms a discontinuous, sheet-like body up to approximately 2 km long and generally less than 20 m thick, controlled by a northeast-plunging shear–fault zone [1,4]. Sulphides occur as massive to semi-massive lenses as well as disseminations and veinlets hosted mainly by carbonate–skarn and quartz-rich rocks, with limited extension into adjacent

black schists. The dominant sulphide assemblage comprises pyrrhotite, chalcopyrite, and sphalerite, with accessory arsenopyrite, cobaltite, Co-pentlandite, and pyrite [1,6]. Chalcopyrite is preferentially associated with quartz-rich domains, whereas sphalerite is more abundant in skarn–carbonate host rocks, reflecting variations in fluid composition and host-rock reactivity during mineralization [6,8].

Resource estimates indicate that the Saramäki deposit contains at least 13.5 Mt of sulphide-bearing material averaging approximately 0.36 wt.% Cu, with locally higher-grade intervals exceeding 1 wt.% Cu and Zn [5]. Although overall metal grades are modest, the high Co/Ni ratios in the sulphides a hallmark of the district and the specific base-metal distributions are characteristic of Outokumpu-type deposits [1,8]. Peltonen et al. [8] proposed that these deposits formed through interaction between metal-enriched hydrothermal fluids and mantle-derived peridotites and reactive metasedimentary rocks during tectonic emplacement and deformation. In the case of Saramäki, the scarcity of ultramafic rocks and the absence of primary syngenetic fuchsite (chromian) quartzites distinguish it from many other deposits in the district, suggesting a stronger structural and hydrothermal control on mineralization [1,4,7]. The quartz-rich mineralized zones are therefore interpreted as structurally controlled veins or silica replacement bodies rather than the classic "Outokumpu-type" quartzites often seen as metasedimentary or exhalative units [1,4].

Overall, Saramäki represents a structurally focused, metasomatically altered Outokumpu-type Cu–Zn system that occupies an intermediate position between classical ultramafic-hosted deposits (like Keretti) and shear-controlled sulphide systems lacking a strong ultramafic association [7,8]. Its geological complexity, metasomatic overprint, and partial concealment beneath glacial cover make it a well-suited test site for evaluating advanced geochemical, biogeochemical, and isotopic exploration methods aimed at detecting deep-seated mineralization.

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III

Figure 1 Geological map of the Outokumpu region and location of Outokumpu-type Cu-Zn-Co-Ni deposits and Ni-Co-Cu deposits (Saramäki deposit and Miihkali massif indicated).

Isotope target-(WP2)

To enhance the detection of distal footprints for the **Saramäki VMS deposit**, this study integrates multi-elemental and isotopic indicators across surface media, utilizing **rock material** from drill cores and **plant samples** as diagnostic tools. By benchmarking surface signals against primary mineralized lithologies, a three-isotope approach (**Sr, Pb, Cu**) will be employed to trace metal migration and source characteristics:

- **Sr Isotope Geochemistry:** Analysis of Sr isotopes in both rock and plant material will be used to characterize the host sequence and assess the degree of water-rock-vegetation interaction. While Sr is highly mobile, it provides a crucial baseline for identifying the influence of radiogenic crustal sources versus the specific hydrothermal signature of the VMS system.
- **Pb Isotope Geochemistry:** Pb isotopes will serve as a robust tracer to distinguish primary magmatic-hydrothermal ore signatures from background environmental signals. By analyzing Pb in mineralized rocks and overhanging vegetation, this task (T2.2) aims to evaluate the efficiency of plant-shuttled isotopic anomalies in reflecting deep-seated VMS mineralization.
- **Cu Isotope Geochemistry:** Given the chalcopyrite-rich nature of VMS systems, Cu isotopes will be targeted to identify redox-driven fractionation processes. This approach

specifically evaluates the utility of Cu isotopes in plant tissues and host rocks as a high-sensitivity tool for mapping the core of the mineralizing system and its surrounding alteration halo.

This integrated isotopic framework is designed to determine if the **Sr, Pb and Cu** signal in surface media can provide a reliable, cost-effective vector for discovering similar buried VMS deposits.

2.2. Fertile Granites and Related Mineralization: Erzgebirge, Germany (WP3)

The Erzgebirge/Krušné Hory metallogenetic province, situated in the northern part of the Bohemian Massif, is renowned for its greisen-hosted lithium (Li) mica systems, which are intimately linked to late Paleozoic highly fractionated leucogranites, also known as rare metal granites [9]. These granites are significantly enriched in critical elements such as Li, tin (Sn), tungsten (W), fluorine (F), rubidium (Rb), cesium (Cs), niobium (Nb), and tantalum (Ta) [9]. The mineralization is associated with hydrothermal alteration, primarily greisenization, which affects the uppermost parts of granite stocks and their surrounding wall rocks [9]. The main host for Li is trioctahedral zinnwaldite, predominantly found in endocontact greisen alteration zones [9]. The regional distribution of Li deposits and prospects suggests that the eastern and central parts of the Erzgebirge/Krušné Hory hold significant potential for expanding known resources, while the western part has lower potential due to deeper erosion.

Based on mineralogical, geochemical, and isotopic criteria, these Variscan Erzgebirge granites are categorized into five distinct groups [10] Figure 2 and Table 1.

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V

Figure 2 Geological sketch-map of the Erzgebirge–Vogtland province illustrating the regional distribution of Variscan granitic types, where western and eastern outcropping complexes contrast with centrally located subsurface bodies like the Markersbach granite (modified from [10]).

Table 1 Granite Classifications of the Erzgebirge District

Granite Type	Key Minerals/Elements	Notable Traits
Eibenstock	Li-mica; high F, high- P_2O_5 , Sn, Li	The most abundant group in the region. S-type.
Kirchtberg	Biotite; low F	Large volume, but lacks specific metal specialization. Transitional S-I-type.
Bergen	Two-mica; low F	Specifically enriched in Tungsten (W). Transitional S-I-type.
Schellerhau	Li-mica; high F, low- P_2O_5 , Sn, Li	High in fluorine but notably depleted in Phosphorus (P). Aluminous A-type.
Gottesberg	Biotite; high F, low- P_2O_5 , Sn	Small bodies/breccia pipes; Sn-specialized but low in P . Aluminous A-type.

Isotope target-(WP3)

To enhance the identification of distal footprints for granite-hosted Li-Sn-W deposits, this study integrates elemental and isotopic indicators across surface media, utilizing rock material

from Task 3.1 drill cores as a benchmark for tracing these signals. A three isotopic approach will be employed:

Sr isotope data play a crucial role in understanding the petrogenesis and source characteristics of the late-collisional granites in the Erzgebirge. Sr isotope data can provide valuable insights into the common crustal origin of biotite and two-mica granites in the Erzgebirge, the high mobility of Sr during differentiation and alteration limits its utility for the highly evolved Li-mica granites [10].

Pb isotope geochemistry will facilitate the dating of primary intrusions (e.g., zircon) and alteration mineral assemblages, while serving as a diagnostic tool to distinguish primary magmatic signatures from secondary alteration effects in soils and vegetation.

Li-isotope geochemistry will be utilized to differentiate geochemical sources, specifically targeting clay minerals in soil and vegetation samples to evaluate the efficacy of Li-isotopes as a rapid, cost-effective analytical tool for mineral exploration.

2.3. Alkaline Metasomatic REE–Zr–Mo Systems: Hůrky, Czech Republic (WP4)

The Hůrky settlement, located within the Čistá-Jesenice Composite Pluton, lies in the immediate vicinity of a significant geological locality characterized by alkaline metasomatic Mo-Zr-REE mineralization. These metasomatites, traditionally referred to as "fenites," have been extensively studied due to their unique mineralogical features and their position within the broader regional framework. The Čistá-Jesenice Composite Pluton itself is a vast, NE-SW trending body covering over 700 km², though its central and northern sections remain largely concealed beneath Permo-Carboniferous and Cretaceous sedimentary cover [11].

The specific mineralization at Hůrky is genetically and spatially associated with the northeastern contact of the Čistá Massif. In this area, the Late Devonian Čistá granodiorite dated to approximately 373 ± 1.1 Ma—intrudes the older, Cambrian-aged Tis granite. The Tis granite is notably mylonitized and serves as the host for the subvertical zones of albite syenite metasomatites. These "fenite" zones reach thicknesses of approximately 200 meters and consist of ductile-deformed bands, with the intensity of both metasomatism and deformation decreasing as one moves away from the contact with the Čistá granodiorite toward the interior of the Tis granite [11].

The mineralogical assembly at Hůrky is remarkably complex, featuring a diverse range of primary and secondary phases. Primary ore minerals include abundant pyrite, galena, molybdenite, and sphalerite, with Hůrky serving as the type locality for the Pb-Bi sulphide heyrovskyite. Secondary minerals, such as ferrimolybdate and Mo-rich jarosite, are also present, particularly within quartz veinlets. Furthermore, the site is known for a rich variety of REE-bearing accessory minerals, including monazite-(Ce), thorianite, and bastnäsite-(Ce). Geochronological data from these systems indicate that the metasomatism occurred around 368.8 ± 1.7 Ma, while Re/Os dating of molybdenite suggests a slightly earlier age of 376 ± 2.4 Ma. Ultimately, the distinct chemical signatures of the feldspars, micas, and metasomatic zircons at Hůrky provide critical insights into the complex hydrothermal and magmatic processes that shaped this metallogenic province [11] Figure 3.

Figure 3 (a) Schematic regional map displaying the geological terranes of Western and Central Europe. (b) Geographical and tectonic setting of the Čistá-Jesenice Composite Pluton within the Teplá-Barrandian Zone of the Bohemian Massif. (c) Detailed geological sketch map of the Čistá-Jesenice Composite Pluton (from [11]).

Isotope target-(WP4)

To achieve these objectives, three primary isotopic approaches will be employed: (1) LA-ICP-MS mapping of zirconosilicate minerals to date time span of the mineralization through Pb gain or loss events; (2) analyzing Sr isotopes by TQ-ICP-MS: magmatic-hydrothermal fluids that cause mobility of the REE, Zr, and Nb are enriched in K and Rb.

The assumption is, this increases the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratio of the mineralized zone compared to the cover rocks to the north of the known mineralization. Migration of fluids from depth to the near surface environment should carry this more radiogenic signature and be expressed in soils and vegetation overlying the potential northerly and southeasterly extensions of

known mineralization; (3) Non-traditional isotopic techniques, specifically Mo isotopes to test if Mo isotopic composition could be part of the distal footprint of such an ore deposit.

3. Target Elements and Isotope Systems

3.1. Sr Isotopes

3.1.1. Principles of Sr Isotope System

Strontium has four naturally occurring isotopes: ^{84}Sr , ^{86}Sr , ^{87}Sr , and ^{88}Sr . Of these, ^{87}Sr is radiogenic, produced by the β -decay of ^{87}Rb with a half-life of 48.8 billion years. The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio in a geological material therefore increases over time as a function of its Rb/Sr ratio, providing both a geochronological tool and a tracer of source compositions [12].

Strontium isotope geochemistry has become an essential tool in economic geology, providing unique insights into the genesis, timing, and fluid sources of diverse mineralization systems. The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio in geological materials reflects the time integrated Rb/Sr ratio of their source regions, making it a powerful tracer of crustal versus mantle contributions, fluid-rock interactions, and hydrothermal processes. Unlike many other isotopic systems, strontium isotopes exhibit minimal mass-dependent fractionation during most geological and biological processes, allowing direct comparison between different sample types and preservation of source signatures through complex geological histories [12].

Recent advances in analytical techniques, particularly multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS) and in situ laser ablation methods, have dramatically improved the precision and spatial resolution of Sr isotope measurements [13, 14]. These developments have enabled new applications including direct dating of ore minerals through Rb-Sr geochronology, high-resolution mapping of fluid flow pathways, and increasingly advanced modeling of fluid mixing processes. Furthermore, the recognition that plant tissues and biogeochemical materials faithfully preserve Sr isotope signatures from underlying bedrock has opened new avenues for mineral exploration in areas with significant overburden or vegetation cover [12, 15, 16].

3.1.2. Mass Spectrometry Techniques

Modern Sr isotope analysis relies primarily on two mass spectrometric techniques: thermal ionization mass spectrometry (TIMS) and multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS). TIMS has traditionally been the gold standard for high-precision Sr isotope measurements, achieving external reproducibility of ± 0.000010 (2σ) or better on $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios [13]. The technique involves loading purified Sr onto a metal filament (typically Re or Ta), ionizing the sample thermally, and measuring isotope ratios in a magnetic sector mass spectrometer.

MC-ICP-MS has emerged as a powerful alternative to TIMS, offering several advantages including faster analysis times, smaller sample requirements, and the ability to analyze solutions directly without the need for filament loading [17, 18]. Modern MC-ICP-MS instruments equipped with collision/reaction cells can achieve precision approaching that of TIMS, with

typical external reproducibility of ± 0.000020 to ± 0.000030 (2σ) on $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios [13, 19]. The technique is particularly well-suited for high-throughput applications and samples with low Sr concentrations, such as plant materials and soil leachates.

Both TIMS and MC-ICP-MS measurements require correction for instrumental mass bias, which is typically accomplished through normalization to a fixed $^{86}\text{Sr}/^{88}\text{Sr}$ Sr ratio (0.1194) assuming exponential mass fractionation. External normalization using the NIST SRM 987 Sr isotope standard (accepted $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ Sr = 0.710248) is routinely employed to ensure inter-laboratory comparability [13].

3.1.3. Sample Preparation and Mineral Selection

Accurate Sr isotope analysis requires careful sample preparation to ensure complete dissolution, efficient separation of Sr from matrix elements (particularly Rb), and minimal contamination. For geological samples, standard procedures involve acid digestion (typically HF-HNO₃-HCl), followed by chromatographic separation using Sr-specific resins [13, 20]. The separation step is critical for removing Rb, which produces isobaric interference on ^{87}Sr , and for reducing matrix effects during mass spectrometry.

For biogeochemical samples (plant tissues, soil leachates), sample preparation protocols must address the high organic content and variable matrix compositions. Complete digestion of organic matter is essential, as incomplete digestion can lead to poor chromatographic separation and biased isotope ratios [21]. Typical procedures involve dry ashing or wet digestion with HNO₃-H₂O₂ mixtures, followed by the same chromatographic separation protocols used for geological samples [17, 22].

Mineral selection for Sr isotope analysis depends on the specific application. For initial Sr isotope ratio determinations, minerals with low Rb/Sr ratios (plagioclase, apatite, barite, carbonate) are preferred because they undergo minimal radiogenic ingrowth and closely preserve initial fluid compositions [12, 23].

3.1.4. In Situ and Micro-analytical Approaches

Recent developments in laser ablation MC-ICP-MS (LA-MC-ICP-MS) have enabled in situ Sr isotope analysis with spatial resolution of 50-100 μm [14, 24]. This capability is particularly valuable for analyzing zoned minerals, identifying multiple fluid events, and dating individual mineral grains without the need for physical separation. The technique has been successfully applied to a wide range of minerals including feldspars, micas, carbonates, and even some sulfides [25].

A significant challenge for in situ Sr isotope analysis is the isobaric interference from ^{87}Rb on ^{87}Sr , which becomes severe in minerals with high Rb/Sr ratios. This limitation has been partially overcome through the development of tandem mass spectrometry (ICP-MS/MS /TQ-ICP-MS) approaches using collision/reaction cells to selectively remove Rb interference [26].

These advances have extended the applicability of in situ Sr isotope analysis to Rb-rich minerals that were previously inaccessible to the technique.

3.2. Pb Isotopes

3.2.1. Principles of Pb Isotope System

Lead isotope geochemistry represents a cornerstone of modern Earth sciences, providing unique constraints on geological processes spanning timescales from millions to billions of years. The utility of Pb isotopes stems from the presence of four naturally occurring isotopes (^{204}Pb , ^{206}Pb , ^{207}Pb , and ^{208}Pb), three of which are radiogenic daughters of long-lived uranium and thorium decay series. This dual nature combining both stable and radiogenic components enables Pb isotopes to serve as powerful chronometers for dating ancient rocks and minerals while simultaneously acting as geochemical tracers for source identification and process characterization [27].

Contemporary Pb isotope geochemistry encompasses diverse applications including U-Th-Pb geochronology for constraining the timing of magmatic, metamorphic, and hydrothermal events; provenance studies of ore deposits and environmental contaminants; and investigations of mantle-crust evolution and planetary differentiation [28, 29]. The field continues to advance rapidly, driven by technological innovations in mass spectrometry, laser ablation systems, and data reduction protocols that collectively push the boundaries of analytical precision, spatial resolution, and sample throughput [30], [31].

The foundation of Pb isotope geochemistry rests on three coupled radioactive decay systems that produce radiogenic Pb isotopes from parent nuclides with distinct half-lives. The ^{238}U decay chain produces ^{206}Pb with a half-life of 4.468 billion years, while ^{235}U decays to ^{207}Pb with a half-life of 704 million years, and ^{232}Th decays to ^{208}Pb with a half-life of 14.05 billion years. The fourth Pb isotope, ^{204}Pb , is non-radiogenic and serves as a reference for normalizing radiogenic isotope ratios. These decay systems operate simultaneously within geological materials, with the relative abundances of radiogenic Pb isotopes evolving as functions of the parent/daughter ratios and time elapsed since system closure [27].

3.2.2. Isotopic Fractionation and Mass Bias

Accurate Pb isotope ratio determination requires rigorous correction for instrumental mass bias, which arises from mass-dependent fractionation during ion transmission, extraction, and detection in mass spectrometers. The magnitude of mass bias can reach several percent per atomic mass unit, far exceeding the natural variations and analytical precision targets for most applications [32]. Multiple correction strategies have been developed to address this challenge, with the choice of method depending on the analytical platform and specific application requirements.

For solution MC-ICP-MS analyses, the thallium normalization method has become widely adopted, exploiting the similar ionization behavior of Tl and Pb in the plasma source [33, 34].

This approach involves doping samples with a Tl standard of known isotopic composition (typically NIST SRM 997) and using the measured $^{205}\text{Tl}/^{203}\text{Tl}$ ratio to calculate the instantaneous mass bias, which is then applied to correct Pb isotope ratios. The method assumes that mass bias follows an exponential, linear, or power law, with the exponential law generally providing the most accurate corrections [33]. Alternative approaches include sample-standard bracketing, where mass bias is interpolated from repeated analyses of reference materials, and internal normalization using double-spike techniques that provide theoretically more robust corrections but require more complex sample preparation [34].

The next generation of analytical device, the analysis of Lead (Pb) isotopes using Triple Quadrupole Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (TQ-ICP-MS) represents a significant advancement in geochronology and environmental science, as it allows for the mitigation of complex spectral interferences that traditionally hindered single-quadrupole systems [35]. While Multi-Collector (MC-ICP-MS) remains the gold standard for high-precision ratios, the TQ-ICP-MS configuration (Q1-CRC-Q2) provides a unique mechanism to resolve the isobaric overlap of ^{204}Hg on the low-abundance ^{204}Pb isotope by using reactive gases like ammonia or oxygen to shift the mercury signal [36].

To achieve geochemically meaningful data, mass bias must be corrected using a mathematical model, most commonly the exponential law, which assumes that the fractionation factor is a function of the mass of the isotopes being measured [37]. One of the most robust methods involves internal normalization using Thallium (NIST SRM 997); since Thallium and Lead have overlapping mass ranges, the measured $^{205}\text{Tl}/^{203}\text{Tl}$ ratio is used to calculate a real-time fractionation factor β that is then applied to the Pb ratios [38]. This internal correction is often combined with External Standard Bracketing (SSB) using NIST SRM 981, which ensures that the long-term drift of the instrument is accounted for by comparing the sample measurements to known isotopic values of a common lead standard throughout the analytical session [39].

3.2.3. Sample Preparation

For solution-based analytical techniques (ID-TIMS and solution MC-ICP-MS), rigorous sample preparation and chemical separation procedures are essential to isolate Pb from matrix elements and potential isobaric interferences. Conventional protocols involve multi-step procedures including sample dissolution, chemical separation using ion exchange chromatography, and purification to remove elements that may cause spectral interferences or suppress ionization efficiency [33,34 and 40].

Sample dissolution typically employs strong acid mixtures (HF-HNO_3 or HCl) in closed vessels to ensure complete breakdown of refractory minerals and quantitative recovery of Pb. For silicate samples, dissolution may require elevated temperatures and extended reaction times to achieve complete digestion. Following dissolution, Pb is separated from matrix elements using anion exchange resins, exploiting the strong affinity of Pb for chloride complexes in HCl media [34,40]. Multiple chromatographic passes may be necessary to achieve the purity re-

quired for high-precision isotope ratio measurements, particularly for samples with high concentrations of elements that form isobaric interferences (e.g., Hg, Tl) or suppress Pb ionization [33].

Blank contamination represents a critical concern in Pb isotope analysis, particularly for samples with low Pb concentrations where even minor contamination can significantly bias measured isotope ratios [40, 41]. Achieving low procedural blanks requires use of high-purity reagents, clean laboratory facilities, and meticulous technique throughout sample preparation. Recent studies have demonstrated that procedural blanks can be reduced to sub-picogram levels through careful optimization of dissolution and separation protocols, enabling precise analysis of increasingly small samples [40, 41].

3.3. Li Isotopes

3.3.1. Principles of the Lithium Isotope System

Lithium possesses two stable isotopes, ${}^6\text{Li}$ (7.5% abundance) and ${}^7\text{Li}$ (92.5% abundance), with a relative mass difference of approximately 16.7%, the largest among all stable isotope systems of metallic elements. This substantial mass difference drives significant isotopic fractionation during geological processes, particularly at or near Earth's surface [42,43]. Lithium isotope compositions are reported in delta notation ($\delta^7\text{Li}$) relative to the LSVEC (lithium carbonate) standard, with natural variations spanning approximately 50‰ [42].

The fundamental principle governing Li isotope fractionation is the preferential partitioning of ${}^6\text{Li}$ into phases or species with weaker bonds, while ${}^7\text{Li}$ concentrates in phases with stronger bonds. This behavior is particularly pronounced during low-temperature processes where kinetic effects dominate [42, 43, 44]. During silicate weathering, secondary minerals preferentially incorporate ${}^6\text{Li}$, leaving residual fluids enriched in ${}^7\text{Li}$ [44, 45]. This fractionation mechanism has established Li isotopes as powerful tracers for continental weathering processes and their response to climate change [44, 46].

Lithium isotope fractionation during fluid-rock interactions is strongly temperature-dependent, with larger fractionations occurring at lower temperatures. This temperature sensitivity enables the use of Li isotopes as a geospeedometer for constraining the timescales of geological processes [42, 47]. In magmatic systems, Li isotope fractionation is generally limited, though measurable variations occur during processes such as diffusion, partial melting, and mineral crystallization [43]. The behavior of Li isotopes during metamorphic dehydration and crustal evolution provides insights into crust-mantle recycling and the search for recycled slab signatures in arc lavas and intraplate basalts [42, 47].

Seawater-basalt interaction represents another critical process where Li isotopes undergo substantial fractionation. During hydrothermal alteration of oceanic crust, Li is mobilized from basalts, with isotopic fractionation controlled by temperature, water-rock ratio, and the nature of secondary minerals formed [42, 48]. These processes contribute to the Li isotopic composition of seawater and influence the global Li cycle [49, 50].

3.3.2. Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation

Rigorous sample preparation and chemical separation procedures are essential for obtaining accurate Li isotope data. The general workflow involves sample digestion, chemical purification through ion-exchange chromatography, and final preparation for instrumental analysis.

Sample digestion methods vary depending on matrix composition. Silicate rocks typically require aggressive acid digestion using HF-HNO₃ mixtures in Teflon vessels, often with heating on hotplates or in high-pressure bombs [51]. Complete dissolution is critical to avoid isotopic fractionation during partial digestion. Carbonate samples can be dissolved using dilute acids (HCl or HNO₃), while aqueous samples may require only acidification and dilution [52]. Special care must be taken to avoid Li contamination from laboratory reagents and materials, necessitating the use of ultra-pure acids and clean laboratory protocols [52,53].

Chemical purification of Li from matrix elements is accomplished through cation-exchange chromatography, typically using AG50W-X8 or AG50W-X12 resin [52, 54, 55]. The separation exploits the differential affinity of cations for the resin in acidic solutions. A typical protocol involves loading the sample in dilute HCl (0.2-0.5 M), eluting matrix elements (Na, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Al) with additional dilute HCl, and finally collecting purified Li in a later fraction [52,54]. The elution profile must be carefully optimized to achieve complete separation of Li from Na, which is particularly important given the large Na/Li ratios in many geological samples [54].

3.4. Mo Isotopes

3.4.1. Principles of the Molybdenum Isotope System

Molybdenum possesses seven stable isotopes (⁹²Mo, ⁹⁴Mo, ⁹⁵Mo, ⁹⁶Mo, ⁹⁷Mo, ⁹⁸Mo, and ¹⁰⁰Mo), with ⁹⁸Mo being the most abundant (24.13%). Molybdenum isotope compositions are typically reported as δ⁹⁸Mo or δ⁹⁷Mo relative to NIST SRM 3134 standard, with natural variations spanning approximately 3‰ [56, 57]. The Mo isotope system has become one of the most powerful paleoredox proxies in geochemistry due to its strong sensitivity to redox conditions and its behavior in aqueous systems [56, 57].

The fundamental principle governing Mo isotope fractionation is the redox-dependent speciation of Mo in natural waters and its subsequent incorporation into sediments. In oxic seawater, Mo exists predominantly as the molybdate ion (MoO₄²⁻), which is highly soluble and exhibits conservative behavior [56, 57]. Under reducing conditions, particularly in euxinic (anoxic and sulfidic) environments, Mo is quantitatively removed from solution through formation of thiomolybdate species (MoO_{4-x}S_x²⁻) and subsequent incorporation into sediments, primarily as Mo-sulfide phases or adsorbed onto organic matter [56, 57, 58].

Isotopic fractionation during Mo removal from seawater depends critically on the redox pathway. In euxinic settings with free H₂S, Mo removal is nearly quantitative with minimal isotopic fractionation (Δ⁹⁸Mo ≈ 0.5-0.7‰), resulting in sediments with δ⁹⁸Mo values close to sea-

water [56, 57, 58]. In contrast, under suboxic conditions where Mn-Fe oxyhydroxides are present, Mo adsorption is accompanied by larger isotopic fractionation ($\Delta^{98}\text{Mo} \approx 2.5\text{-}3.0\text{‰}$), producing sediments with lighter Mo isotope compositions [56, 57]. This differential fractionation behavior enables reconstruction of ancient ocean redox conditions from sedimentary Mo isotope records [56, 58].

3.4.2. Analytical Protocols for Molybdenum Isotopes

Analytical protocols typically involve monitoring multiple Mo isotopes (^{92}Mo , ^{94}Mo , ^{95}Mo , ^{96}Mo , ^{97}Mo , ^{98}Mo , ^{100}Mo) simultaneously on Faraday collectors [59]. Careful attention must be paid to isobaric interferences, particularly from Zr and Ru, which can be problematic if not completely removed during chemical separation [60, 61, 62]. Typical sample concentrations for analysis range from 50-200 ppb Mo, with total Mo requirements of 50-200 ng for high-precision double-spike measurements [59].

Quality assurance includes regular analysis of reference materials and inter-laboratory comparison samples. The NIST SRM 3134 Mo standard serves as the zero-point for the $\delta^{98}\text{Mo}$ scale, while secondary standards such as NIST SRM 610 glass and various rock standards enable method validation [59]. Malinovsky et al. contributed to establishing Mo isotope ratio measurement protocols on geological samples by MC-ICP-MS, providing foundational methodological guidance [63].

3.4.3. Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation

Rigorous sample preparation and chemical separation are essential for accurate Mo isotope analysis, particularly given the low Mo concentrations in many geological materials and the potential for isobaric interferences [64]. The general workflow involves sample digestion, chemical purification through column chromatography, and final preparation for instrumental analysis.

Sample digestion methods depend on matrix composition and Mo speciation. Silicate rocks typically require aggressive acid digestion using HF-HNO₃-HCl mixtures in Teflon vessels or high-pressure bombs [60]. For samples containing refractory Mo-bearing phases, fusion with alkali fluxes may be necessary to ensure complete dissolution [60]. Carbonate samples can be dissolved using diluted acids, though care must be taken to avoid Mo loss through volatilization. Organic-rich sediments may require oxidative digestion using HNO₃-H₂O₂ mixtures to destroy organic matter before Mo extraction.

Chemical purification of Mo from matrix elements is accomplished through anion-exchange chromatography, exploiting the strong affinity of Mo oxyanions for anion-exchange resins in acidic solutions [60, 62]. Pearce et al. developed a widely adopted method for quantitative separation of Mo and Re from geological materials for isotopic determination by MC-ICP-MS [61]. This protocol uses AG1-X8 anion-exchange resin in a multi-step procedure: samples

are loaded in 0.5 M HCl, matrix elements are eluted with additional 0.5 M HCl, interfering elements (particularly Zr and Ru) are removed with 2 M HNO₃, and finally Mo is collected in 6 M HCl or 2 M HNO₃-0.5 M HF [60, 61]. Li et al. presented an enhanced method for Mo separation and isotopic determination using a novel chromatographic extraction technique, improving separation efficiency and reducing procedural blanks [60]. Migeon et al. developed an enhanced method specifically for Mo separation in uranium-rich materials and geological samples, addressing challenges posed by high-U matrices [62]. These advances have expanded the range of materials amenable to Mo isotope analysis and improved data quality [60, 62].

3.4.4. In Situ and Micro-Analytical Approaches

In situ analytical techniques for Mo isotopes have developed more recently than for Li or Cu, driven by the need to analyze Mo isotope variations in minerals, particularly molybdenite, and to investigate spatial heterogeneity in ore deposits and magmatic systems [65]. Laser ablation multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-MC-ICP-MS) has emerged as the primary technique for in situ Mo isotope analysis [65].

Tian et al. developed methods for in situ precise determination of stable Mo isotope ratios in molybdenite using femtosecond LA-MC-ICP-MS, achieving precision of $\pm 0.15\%$ (2σ) for $\delta^{98}\text{Mo}$ [65]. This represents a significant advance, as molybdenite is the primary Mo ore mineral and records Mo isotope signatures of ore-forming fluids [65, 66]. Femtosecond laser systems offer advantages over nanosecond lasers, including reduced elemental and isotopic fractionation during ablation and more consistent ablation behavior [65].

The development of molybdenite reference materials has been critical for in situ Mo isotope analysis. Tian et al. synthesized molybdenite reference materials specifically for in situ Mo and S isotope measurement using LA-MC-ICP-MS, providing well-characterized standards with homogeneous isotopic compositions [65]. These reference materials enable accurate calibration and quality control for in situ measurements, addressing a major limitation in earlier work [65].

Challenges for in situ Mo isotope analysis include managing matrix effects, achieving sufficient precision for geological applications, and dealing with the relatively low abundance of Mo in many minerals [65, 66]. Matrix-matched standards are essential, as differences in major element composition between samples and standards can introduce systematic errors [65, 66]. The precision of in situ measurements ($\pm 0.15\text{-}0.30\%$, 2σ) is lower than solution MC-ICP-MS but sufficient for many applications where spatial resolution is critical [65, 66].

3.5. Cu Isotopes

3.5.1. Principles of the Copper Isotope System

Copper possesses two stable isotopes, ⁶³Cu (69.17% abundance) and ⁶⁵Cu (30.83% abundance), with a relative mass difference of approximately 3.2%. Copper isotope compositions

are reported in delta notation ($\delta^{65}\text{Cu}$) relative to NIST SRM 976 standard, with natural variations spanning approximately 20‰ [67]. The Cu isotope system has emerged as a powerful tracer for redox-dependent processes, ore deposit formation, and biological fractionation [68, 69].

The fundamental principle governing Cu isotope fractionation is the preferential partitioning of isotopes between different oxidation states and coordination environments. Copper exists in three oxidation states in nature: Cu^0 (native copper), Cu^+ (cuprous), and Cu^{2+} (cupric), with significant isotopic fractionation occurring during redox transitions [68, 69]. Theoretical and experimental studies indicate that ^{65}Cu preferentially partitions into oxidized species (Cu^{2+}) and phases with stronger bonds, while ^{63}Cu concentrates in reduced species (Cu^+ , Cu^0) and phases with weaker bonds [68].

Copper isotope fractionation is particularly pronounced during low-temperature processes where kinetic effects dominate. During weathering and oxidation of Cu-bearing sulfides, heavier Cu isotopes are preferentially mobilized into solution, leaving residual minerals enriched in light Cu isotopes [68, 70]. This fractionation mechanism has established Cu isotopes as tracers for ore deposit weathering, supergene enrichment, and environmental Cu cycling [68, 70].

Copper isotopes also exhibit significant fractionation during biological processes. Balter et al. documented natural variations of Cu and S stable isotopes in blood of hepatocellular carcinoma patients, revealing that Cu isotope fractionation is driven by competing redox states and ligand preferences [71]. Weinstein et al. investigated isotopic fractionation of Cu in plants, demonstrating that biological uptake and translocation processes produce measurable Cu isotope variations [72]. These findings have opened new applications for Cu isotopes in biomedical and environmental research [71, 72].

3.5.2. Analytical Methodologies for Copper Isotopes

Multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS) has become the dominant technique for high-precision Cu isotope analysis, offering superior precision, sample throughput, and flexibility compared to earlier TIMS methods [73].

The standard approach for mass bias correction in Cu isotope analysis is sample-standard bracketing, where samples are measured between repeated analyses of the NIST SRM 976 Cu standard. This technique assumes that instrumental mass bias varies smoothly over time and can be interpolated between standard measurements. Some laboratories employ Zn doping for internal normalization, adding a Zn standard solution to both samples and standards and using the known Zn isotope ratio to correct for mass bias [71]. This approach can improve precision and reduce sensitivity to instrumental drift. Analytical protocols typically involve monitoring ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu simultaneously on Faraday collectors, with careful attention to iso-

baric interferences and baseline corrections [73, 74]. The most significant potential interference is from $^{40}\text{Ar}^{23}\text{Na}^+$ on $^{63}\text{Cu}^+$, which can be problematic if Na is not completely removed during chemical separation [74, 75]. Typical sample concentrations for analysis range from 100-500 ppb Cu, with total Cu requirements of 50-200 ng for high-precision measurements [73, 74].

3.5.3. Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation

Careful processing is required to isolate copper from other elements before analysis. This is essential for two reasons: it avoids the high risk of environmental Cu contamination and ensures that matrix elements do not interfere with the isotopic signal. The standard procedure involves breaking down the sample matrix, separating the target element from interferences through chemical purification, and preparing the purified extract for the instrument [73].

Different matrices require specific digestion techniques: silicates are treated with HF-HNO₃-HCl mixtures under heat or high pressure; sulfides are dissolved in aqua regia; and biological tissues are digested via microwave with HNO₃ and H₂O₂. Because copper is a common contaminant, the use of high-purity acids and clean-room standards is essential to maintain accurate isotopic signatures. Chemical purification of Cu from matrix elements is accomplished through anion-exchange chromatography, typically using AG1-X8 or AG MP-1 resin [76]. The separation exploits the strong affinity of Cu²⁺ chloro-complexes for anion-exchange resins in concentrated HCl solutions. A typical protocol involves loading the sample in 7-8 M HCl, eluting matrix elements (Fe, Zn, Na, K, Ca, Mg, Al) with additional 7 M HCl, and finally collecting purified Cu in dilute HCl or HNO₃ [76].

4. High-Resolution Elemental Analysis Using TQ-ICP-MS

4.1. Fundamental Architecture

Triple quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (TQ-ICP-MS) represents a transformative advancement in high-precision isotopic analysis and trace elemental determination. The tandem mass selection architecture, featuring two quadrupole mass filters separated by a collision/reaction cell (CRC), enables unprecedented control over spectral interferences that have historically limited single-quadrupole ICP-MS performance. Key innovations include the use of reactive gases (CH₃F, NH₃, O₂, H₂) for on-line mass-shift reactions, elimination of matrix separation requirements for isotope analysis, and achievement of precision levels approaching multi-collector ICP-MS (MC-ICP-MS) for certain applications. TQ-ICP-MS has found extensive applications across geochemistry, environmental monitoring, materials science, biomedical research, and forensic investigations Figure 4.

The TQ-ICP-MS system begins with sample introduction via a conventional nebulizer into the inductively coupled plasma, which operates at atmospheric pressure and temperatures exceeding 6000 K. The plasma efficiently ionizes sample constituents, producing predominantly singly charged positive ions. These ions are extracted through a differentially pumped interface consisting of sampler and skimmer cones, which separate the atmospheric-pressure plasma from the high-vacuum mass analyzer region [77]. A quartz tube connects the plasma torch to the interface cones, and ion optics (including extraction lenses and focusing elements) guide the ion beam toward the first quadrupole.

The first quadrupole mass filter (Q1) performs initial mass selection, transmitting only ions within a narrow mass-to-charge (m/z) window while rejecting matrix components and potential interferences at other masses. This pre-selection step is critical for reducing the chemical complexity entering the collision/reaction cell and minimizing unwanted side reactions [77]. In MS/MS mode, Q1 operates in mass-selective mode, transmitting only the target analyte isotopes. In alternative scanning modes, Q1 can be operated in RF-only mode to transmit all ions, though this sacrifices the primary advantage of tandem mass selection.

The collision/reaction cell (CRC) represents the heart of the TQ-ICP-MS system and distinguishes it from single-quadrupole instruments. The CRC is a pressurized multipole ion guide (typically a hexapole or octupole) filled with a reactive or collision gas at pressures ranging from 10^{-3} to 10^{-2} mbar [77]. Within the CRC, mass-selected ions from Q1 undergo controlled ion-molecule reactions or collisional processes that selectively transform target analytes while leaving interferences unreacted, or vice versa. The choice of reaction gas and cell pressure determines the reaction chemistry and efficiency. Common reaction gases include CH_3F and N_2O for Sr isotope analysis [77], NH_3 for rare earth elements, O_2 for transition metals, and H_2 for collision-induced dissociation of polyatomic ions [78].

The second quadrupole mass filter (Q2) performs post-reaction mass selection, transmitting only the desired reaction product ions to the detector while rejecting unreacted precursor ions, unwanted reaction products, and any remaining interferences [77]. This second stage of mass filtering is the defining feature that differentiates TQ-ICP-MS from single-quadrupole systems with reaction cells. In single-quadrupole instruments, all ions exiting the reaction cell (both products and unreacted species) are transmitted to the detector, which can lead to incomplete interference removal and elevated backgrounds. The double mass selection in TQ-ICP-MS ensures that only the intended product ions reach the detector, dramatically improving signal-to-noise ratios and measurement accuracy.

Triple Quadrupole ICP-MS (TQ-ICP-MS) Schematic

Figure 4 Schematic diagram of triple quadrupole ICP-MS (TQ-ICP-MS) instrumentation showing the complete ion pathway from sample introduction through detection. The system comprises an inductively coupled plasma (ICP) ion source, interface region with sampler and skimmer cones, ion optics, first quadrupole mass filter (Q1), collision/reaction cell (CRC), second quadrupole mass filter (Q2), and ion detector.

4.2. Analytical Protocols for Targeted Isotope System

4.2.1. Strontium (Sr) Isotope Analysis

The main difficulty in measuring Strontium $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ is the interference from Rubidium ^{87}Rb , which usually requires a slow chemical separation process. TQ-ICP-MS solves this using a specific gas like CH_3F , O_2 Figure 5 and N_2O in the reaction cell:

- **The Process:** For example, the first quadrupole (Q1) selects Sr ions, which then react with the gas to form a heavier molecule SrF^+ . The final quadrupole (Q2) measures these new molecules.
- **The Benefit:** Because Rubidium does not react with this gas, it is left behind, completely removing the interference [77].
- **Performance:** While not as ultra-precise as Multi-Collector (MC-ICP-MS) systems, this method is accurate enough (0.05% precision) for most environmental and geological studies and works well even on very small samples [79].

Figure 5 ^{87}Sr determination via O_2 mass-shift mode in ICP-QQQ [21].

4.3. Lead (Pb) Isotope Analysis

Lead analysis is challenged by overlaps from Mercury ^{204}Hg on ^{204}Pb and other combined molecules. The following three modes were evaluated to optimize the analytical performance of the Triple Quadrupole ICP-MS:

- **No Gas (SQ Mode):** Operates as a **Single Quadrupole** system without reaction cell gases. In this configuration, **Q1** functions simply as an ion guide, providing no mass filtering before the cell.
- **Bandpass (SQ Mode):** Utilizes **ammonia (NH_3)** as a reaction gas within a **Single Quadrupole** setup. Here, **Q1** acts as a broad bandpass filter to exclude a range of non-target masses.
- **MS/MS (Mass Filter Mode):** Employs **ammonia (NH_3)** reaction gas in a true **tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS)** configuration. **Q1** functions as a high-precision mass filter, isolated at unit mass resolution to ensure only specific ions enter the reaction cell Figure 6.
- **Efficiency:** This allows scientists to measure Lead in complex environmental samples, like cave sediments, without having to chemically purify the sample first [80].
- **Precision Boost:** Techniques like the "concentration-gradient method" can further improve the accuracy of these measurements by comparing different sample concentrations [81].

Figure 6 Schematic of ^{204}Hg interference removal via TQ-ICP-MS reaction cell NH_3 [80].

4.3.1. Other Isotope Systems (Li, Cu, Mo)

Lithium has two stable isotopes (${}^6\text{Li}$ and ${}^7\text{Li}$) with a relatively large mass difference, making Li isotope ratio measurements susceptible to significant mass bias effects. The primary spectral interferences for Li include ${}^6\text{LiH}^+$ on ${}^7\text{Li}^+$ and various polyatomic species in complex matrices. TQ-ICP-MS can potentially address these interferences through collision-induced dissociation using H_2 or He as collision gases, though specific protocols for Li isotope analysis by TQ-ICP-MS were not extensively covered in the retrieved literature.

Copper isotope analysis (${}^{63}\text{Cu}/{}^{65}\text{Cu}$) is important for environmental tracing, biogeochemical cycling studies, and materials provenance. The main spectral interferences for Cu include ${}^{40}\text{Ar}{}^{23}\text{Na}^+$ on ${}^{63}\text{Cu}^+$ and ${}^{32}\text{S}{}^{33}\text{S}^+$ on ${}^{65}\text{Cu}^+$. TQ-ICP-MS protocols could employ O_2 as a reaction gas to form CuO^+ product ions, shifting the measurement away from these polyatomic interferences. The double mass selection would ensure that only CuO^+ ions reach the detector, eliminating contributions from unreacted interferences.

Molybdenum has seven stable isotopes (${}^{92}\text{Mo}$, ${}^{94}\text{Mo}$, ${}^{95}\text{Mo}$, ${}^{96}\text{Mo}$, ${}^{97}\text{Mo}$, ${}^{98}\text{Mo}$, ${}^{100}\text{Mo}$), and Mo isotope ratio measurements are valuable for redox condition reconstruction in paleoceanography and environmental studies. The primary spectral interferences for Mo include ${}^{40}\text{Ar}$ -based polyatomic species and isobaric interferences from Zr isotopes. TQ-ICP-MS could address these interferences through mass-shift reactions, though specific protocols were not detailed in the available literature.

The general principles established for Sr and Pb isotope analysis by TQ-ICP-MS including careful selection of reaction gases, optimization of CRC conditions, implementation of robust mass bias correction protocols, and validation using certified reference materials are directly applicable to Li, Cu, and Mo isotope systems. Future research of T2.2 will focus on developing and validating specific TQ-ICP-MS protocols for these important isotope systems.

5. Preliminary Results of Isotope and Elemental Concentration by using TQ-ICP-MS

5.1. Analytical Protocols and Sample Preparation for Elemental Concentration and Isotope Measurement by using TQ-ICP-MS

5.1.1. Sample Homogenization and Digestion and Protocol for the Trace Elements Analysis by TQ-ICP-MS

The analytical workflow begins with the physical preparation of the material, where samples are crushed and powdered to ensure complete homogenization Figure 7 and

Table 2. For each analysis, approximately 100 to 200 mg of the homogenized powder is precisely weighed into Teflon digestion vessels. To ensure data quality and identify potential contamination, duplicate samples are selected for 10% to 15% of the total batch, and a procedural blank (PB-1) containing only the acid reagents is prepared alongside the samples.

The digestion process utilizes a mixture of 4 ml concentrated HNO_3 and 2 ml of H_2O_2 . The vessels are loaded into a specialized rotor and processed via microwave-assisted digestion using a specific plant material program. This method involves a 10-minute ramp period to reach 200°C followed by a 20-minute plateau at that temperature to ensure the total breakdown of the sample matrix Figure.

5.1.2. Post-Digestion Processing and Vessel Maintenance

Once the vessels have cooled to room temperature, the digested solutions are transferred into labeled Savillex containers. To ensure quantitative recovery of the analyte, the digestion vessels are rinsed with 2 ml of deionized water, which is then combined with the initial extract.

A rigorous cleaning protocol is maintained for the Teflon hardware to prevent cross-contamination. This involves a secondary microwave cycle using a cleaning solution of 1.5 ml HCl , 3 ml HNO_3 , and 4 ml of water. After cooling, the vessels are rinsed again and allowed to dry overnight on clean laboratory wipes in a controlled environment.

5.1.3. Clean Laboratory Procedures and Instrumental Analysis

The final preparation stage occurs within a clean laboratory environment to protect the integrity of the trace element signatures. The digested samples are placed on a hot plate at 85°C and evaporated to total dryness overnight. The resulting residue is then reconstituted in a 2% HNO_3 solution, and the final dilution weight is recorded to calculate the ultimate concentration factors.

Prior to measurement, the solutions are filtered to remove any remaining particulate matter and transferred into labeled vials. These purified samples are then introduced into the TQ-ICP-MS for the simultaneous analysis of major and trace elements. The final stage of the protocol involves comprehensive data reduction, where raw instrumental counts are converted into concentration values by applying the necessary dilution and correction factors Figure 11.

Figure 7 Overview of sample selection and preparation procedures for trace element and isotopic analysis via TQ-ICP-MS.

5.1.4. Sample Inventory and Analytical Objectives

We utilize a diverse suite of plant materials, categorized by their origin and intended analytical purpose. These include experimental testing samples, project-specific materials for laboratory inter-comparison, and international reference materials (RMs) for data validation.

Experimental and Testing Samples (Black Tea)

A total of four black tea samples were sourced for initial testing and homogenization trials. Three of these originate from the Nonsuch Tea Estate in the Nilgiris region of South India, representing different leaf grades. The finest grade may potentially be analyzed without prior milling, depending on the sample mass required for homogeneity; however, standard mechanical grinding is recommended for all tea samples to ensure consistency. A fourth sample, sourced from a Chinese producer, is provided specifically to evaluate the milling efficiency of larger plant tissues. While the Chinese sample is of food-grade quality, the Indian samples are strictly for analytical use, as field observations during collection suggest they may exceed European pesticide residue limits.

Figure 8 Sample preparation and acid digestion process for TQ-ICP-MS analysis.

Project-Specific Reference Materials

SEMACRET Project: Two samples are included that have been previously analyzed by MASA. These serve as a primary tool for inter-laboratory validation, allowing for a direct comparison between current results and established values.

UPDEEP Project: Three reference materials consisting of spruce and pine tissues are included. These samples have been characterized by MASA and four additional laboratories. While these materials are known to exhibit some degree of inter-bottle inhomogeneity, they are considered stable within individual aliquots.

International Reference Materials

For global validation and traceability, two internationally recognized reference materials are employed:

White Clover RM: A standardized botanical material.

NIST Standard: Provided in its original manufacturer packaging to serve as the primary anchor for acknowledging absolute concentrations (**Error! Reference source not found.**) and validating the accuracy of the analytical run.

Figure 9 Sample preparation for Sr separation via ion-exchange chromatography columns.

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[Analytical protocols]

Table 2 Summary of sample weights, final dilution weights, and calculated dilution factors.

Sample ID	Sample wt (g)	Vessels#	Dilution wt (g)	Dilution factor
BT-NI	0.292	9	20.6003	70.5489726
Dup-BT-KUA	0.278	15	21.1281	76.00035971
U-NEED	0.29	6	22.0408	76.00275862
BT-KUA	0.277	8	21.4655	77.49277978
BT-NII	0.272	10	21.8923	80.48639706
U-TWIG	0.244	5	20.2003	82.78811475
BT-NIII	0.264	11	21.9062	82.9780303
CRM(No. 1169)	0.258	14	21.7008	84.11162791
SEMA-201	0.233	3	20.321	87.21459227
Dup-SEMA-201	0.241	18	21.1812	87.88879668
Dup-U-TWIG	0.253	16	22.5099	88.97193676
White cloves	0.243	13	21.7433	89.47860082
SEMA-221	0.234	1	20.9998	89.74273504
U-BARK	0.222	4	20.1995	90.98873874
WASTE	N/A	19	_____	_____
PB-1	N/A	20	21.6787	_____

Figure 10 Bar chart showing trace element concentrations (ppb) from samples measured by TQ-ICP-MS.

Figure 11 Dilution factor for selected samples after digestion.

5.2. Strontium (Sr) Isotope Method Development and Protocol Testing

5.2.1. Sample Preparation and Chemical Separation

The analytical procedure for Strontium isotope testing began with the acid digestion of various Certified Reference Materials (CRMs). The digestion utilized a concentrated mixture of HNO₃,

HCl, HF on a hotplate maintained at 185°C To eliminate fluoride precipitates, samples underwent a secondary refluxing stage using a mixture of H_3BO_3 and concentrated HCl. Following digestion, the solutions were split into two aliquots: one for total digestion (matrix-on) analysis and another for purified Sr separation. Strontium fractions were isolated using the Prepfast system following the Kidder et al., 2021 [82] method, after which samples were dried down and reconstituted in HNO_3 for instrumental introduction Table 3 and Figure 9 .

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[Analytical protocols]

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Table 3 Ion-exchange chromatography methods for Cu, Mo, and Sr [82].

Step	Cu Purification	Mo Purification	Sr Purification
Stage	(1) Pre-purification	(1) Pre-purification	(1) Purification
Column / Resin	9 cm / 3 mL (AG 50W-X12)	3 cm / 600 μ L (AG 50W-X12)	3 cm / 200 μ L (Sr Spec)
Wash	6 mL 6.5M HCl	6 mL 6.5M HCl	4 mL 8M HNO ₃
Condition	3 mL 1M HCl	3 mL 0.5M HCl	1 mL 3M HNO ₃
Sample Load	200 μ L 1M HCl	200 μ L 0.5M HCl	1 mL 3M HNO ₃
Matrix Removal	21 mL 1M HCl	—	3 mL 3M HNO ₃
Elution	11 mL 2M HCl (Cu)	6 mL 1M HCl (Mo)	1 mL 0.05M HNO ₃ (Sr)
Stage	(2) Purification	(2) Purification	—
Source	Borroch et al. (2008)	Pearce et al. (2010)	—
Column / Resin	4 cm / 1 mL (AG MP-1)	3 cm / 200 μ L (AG 1-X8)	—
Wash	6 mL ultra-pure H ₂ O	4 mL 8M HNO ₃ / 1.5 mL 2M HNO ₃ / 3.5 mL 3M HCl	—
Condition	5 mL 9M HCl	1.5 mL 1M HF / 0.5M HCl	—
Sample Load	200 μ L 9M HCl	300 μ L 1M HF / 0.5M HCl	—
Matrix Removal	4 mL 9M HCl	1.5 mL 1M HF / 0.5M HCl / 3 mL 3M HCl	—
Elution	15 mL 5M HCl (Cu)	2.5 mL 2M HCl (Mo)	—

5.2.2. TQ-ICP-MS Method Optimization

Initial method development focused on establishing optimal timing parameters for sample-standard bracketing using NIST SRM 987 as the primary standard and SLRS-6 as the unknown.

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Operating in TQ-O₂ mode, a series of trials were conducted to synchronize dwell times, sweeps, and repeats with the required uptake time.

- First, four different timing configurations were tested, determining that an uptake time of 85 to 90 seconds was necessary for signal stability.
- Then, the protocol was refined to an 85-second uptake time across all trials. The most effective configuration identified during this phase utilized a 0.05-second dwell time, 50 sweeps, and 10 repeats to maximize data density Table 4.

Table 4 Summary of analytical run and integration parameters for TQ-ICP-MS protocol testing.

Run name	Integration time	Sweeps	Replicates (x)
Run 1 (0.05 s) – 50 sweeps, 3x	0.05 s	50	3
Run 2 (0.05 s) – 25 sweeps, 15x	0.05 s	25	15
Run 2b (0.05 s) – 25 sweeps, 10x	0.05 s	25	10
Run 3 (0.05 s) – 30 sweeps, 10x	0.05 s	30	10
Run 4 (0.1 s) – 30 sweeps, 5x	0.1 s	30	5
Run 5 (0.1 s) – 30 sweeps, 10x	0.1 s	30	10
Run 6 (0.1 s) – 50 sweeps, 5x	0.1 s	50	5
Run 7 (0.05 s) – 50 sweeps, 10x	0.05 s	50	10

Each column title contains measurement parameters:

- **(0.05s)** → *Integration time per sweep* — how long the instrument counts ions for each reading.
- **50 sweeps** → *Number of sweeps per replicate* — the instrument repeats the signal measurement 50 times to improve precision.
- **3x, 10x, 15x, etc.** → *Number of replicates* — how many times the whole 50-sweep measurement is repeated for that sample.

Run 1 (0.05s) – 50 sweeps, 3x”

means: each replicate had 50 sweeps with 0.05 s integration time, repeated 3 times.

5.2.3. Reaction Gas Performance and Matrix Interference

Subsequent testing compared the effectiveness of different reaction gases in mitigating interferences. Total digests and Sr separation samples were analyzed using TQ-O₂ however, results for the total digestion samples were significantly inaccurate. Transitioning to TQ-O₂ did not resolve the discrepancy in the total digestion results, even after diluting the samples to match the concentration of NIST 987 (approximately 10–30 ppb) and adjusting dwell times for the oxide masses ⁸⁷Sr¹⁶O and ⁸⁶Sr¹⁶O.

Further investigations explored hardware tuning variations, including switching Extraction Lens 1 and Q1 Bias from positive to negative polarities. Despite these adjustments, the isotopic ratios for the total digestion CRMs remained "off," suggesting that the hardware tuning was not the primary source of the analytical bias.

5.2.4. Rb-Doping Tests and Matrix Influence

To investigate whether the inaccurate total digestion results were caused by residual Rubidium ⁸⁷Rb interferences, a series of SLRS-6 samples were doped with increasing amounts of Rb and analyzed. The results for the Rb-doped samples were accurate, confirming that the N₂O mass-shift was effectively removing the Rb isobaric interference.

This finding indicated that the inaccuracies in the total digestion samples were likely caused by a matrix effect rather than a spectral overlap. The validated N₂O protocol was applied to vegetation samples. While the total vegetation digests continued to show matrix-related issues, the purified Sr fractions from the same vegetation materials were successfully analyzed, demonstrating that chemical separation remains the most reliable pathway for high-precision results in complex organic matrices.

5.2.5. Standard Reference Materials (SRMs) for Sr Isotopic Analysis

This section outlines the Standard Reference Materials (SRMs) utilized for validating Sr chemical separation (via ion-exchange chromatography) and total acid digestion procedures. These standards are essential for ensuring the accuracy and external reproducibility of the Sr isotope Standard-Sample Bracketing (SSB) protocol during TQ-ICP-MS analysis.

5.2.6. Key Components of the Protocol

Total Digestion Validation: Using certified geological powders (e.g., NIST SRMs or USGS Rock Standards like BCR-2 or BHVO-2) to ensure complete matrix breakdown and Sr recovery

RM's name	Accepted value	Corrected value (Average)
GSP-2 - Sr separation	0.765	0.7653

and ence not Sr tion try): tion of Sr tion from elements cally Rb, REEs) resin- tion. ard-	GSP-2 - total digestion	0.765	0.8307	Error! Refer- source found..
	JB-2 - Sr separation	0.7037	0.7032	
	JB-2 - total digestion	0.7037	0.7856	
	PCC-1 - Sr separation	0.7111	0.7312	Separa- (Column Chemis-
	PCC-1- total digestion	0.7111	0.7529	
	GSP-1 - Sr separation	0.767	0.7699	Verifica-
	GSP-1 - total digestion	0.767	0.8256	
	BIR-1 - Sr separation	0.7031	0.7054	purifica-
	BIR-1 - total digestion	0.7031	0.7834	
	AGV-1 - Sr separation	0.7040	0.7035	(specifi-
	AGV-1 - total digestion	0.7040	0.7210	
	BHVO-1 - Sr separation	0.7035	0.7013	Ca, and using based separa-
	BHVO-1 - total digestion	0.7035	0.7452	
	JG-3 - Sr separation	0.7035	0.7052	Stand- Sample
JG-3 - total digestion	0.7035	0.7267		
JA-3 - total digestion	0.7042	0.7363		

Bracketing (SSB): The application of a primary isotopic standard (typically NIST SRM 987) for Sr isotope to bracket unknown samples. This corrects for instrumental mass bias and drift during the analytical session.

Table 5 Summary of Standard Reference Materials (SRMs) used for Sr separation and total digestion in the Sr isotope standard-sample bracketing (SSB) protocol.

RM's name	Accepted value	Corrected value (Average)
GSP-2 - Sr separation	0.765	0.7653
GSP-2 - total digestion	0.765	0.8307
JB-2 - Sr separation	0.7037	0.7032
JB-2 - total digestion	0.7037	0.7856
PCC-1 - Sr separation	0.7111	0.7312
PCC-1- total digestion	0.7111	0.7529
GSP-1 - Sr separation	0.767	0.7699
GSP-1 - total digestion	0.767	0.8256

BIR-1 - Sr separation	0.7031	0.7054
BIR-1 - total digestion	0.7031	0.7834
AGV-1 - Sr separation	0.7040	0.7035
AGV-1 - total digestion	0.7040	0.7210

Figure 12 Bar chart comparing accepted values and corrected of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratio measured by TQ-ICP-MS.

5.3. Thermo Scientific iCAP TQ ICP-MS Parameters for Strontium Isotope Measurement

5.3.1. Plasma and Interface Parameters

The analysis is conducted using a high-energy plasma, with the Radio Frequency (RF) Power maintained at 1550 W to ensure efficient atomization and ionization of the sample. To optimize the ion extraction from the plasma into the mass spectrometer, the Sampling Depth is precisely set to 5.00 mm. The transport of the aerosolized sample into the torch is controlled by a Nebulizer Gas Flow Rate ranging between **0.94 and 0.96 L/min**, which balances signal stability with sensitivity Table 6.

5.3.2. Reaction Cell Conditions

To overcome the isobaric interference of ^{87}Rb on ^{87}Sr , the instrument utilizes a reaction cell with specific gas flows. The Cell Gas Flow Rate is configured to use either 0.18–0.20 mL/min

of Nitrous Oxide N₂O or 0.3 mL/min of Oxygen O₂. These gases react chemically with the Strontium ions to "shift" them to a higher mass, while the Rubidium remains largely unreacted at its original mass.

5.3.3. Mass Selection and MS/MS Transitions

The instrument operates in MS/MS (double mass filter) mode to isolate the isotopes of interest. For the measurement of ⁸⁶Sr, the first quadrupole (Q1) is set to m/z 86, while the second quadrupole (Q2) is set to m/z 102 to detect the reacted oxide product ⁸⁶Sr¹⁶O⁺. Similarly, for the radiogenic ⁸⁷Sr isotope, Q1 filters for m/z 87, and Q2 is set to m/z 103 to measure the resulting ⁸⁷Sr¹⁶O⁺ ion.

5.3.4. Data Acquisition Settings

The precision of the isotopic ratios is managed through a structured acquisition sequence consisting of 10 Replicates, with each replicate being the result of 50 Sweeps across the designated mass range. The Integration Time (or dwell time) for each individual mass is set to 0.1 seconds for both the N₂O and O₂ reaction modes, ensuring a sufficient count rate for high-quality geochronological or tracer data.

Table 6 Thermo Scientific iCAP TQ ICP-MS parameters for Strontium (Sr) isotope measurement.

Parameter	Setting
RF Power (W)	1550
Sampling Depth (mm)	5.00
Nebulizer Gas Flow Rate (L/min)	0.94-0.96 (L/min)
Cell Gas Flow Rate (mL/min)	0.18-0.20 N ₂ O 0.3 O ₂
Q1 -> Q2 Masses (m/z)	86 -> 102 87 -> 103
Replicates	10
Sweeps	50
Integration Time of Each Mass (s) (Dwell time)	0.1 (N ₂ O & O ₂)

6. Application of Sr Isotope Method Development on Plant Samples for Total Digestion and Sr Separation

Table 7 shows the isotopic composition of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ values across a diverse set of samples (e.g., U-NEED, BT-NIII, PL-1) and certified reference materials (e.g., AGV-1, GSP-1, and SLRS6). For each entry, the table provides the measured mean ratio, the Standard Deviation (STD), and the Relative Standard Deviation (RSD %). To ensure analytical rigor, the dataset includes duplicate analyses (denoted by the suffix "_dup") and benchmarks these results against "Accepted Values" and published data from GeoReM and Murphy et al. (2019).

The precision of the measurements is consistently high, with RSD values primarily falling between 0.26% and 0.86%. The reproducibility between original samples and their duplicates—such as SEMA-221 (0.769) and SEMA-221_dup (0.769)—is excellent. This consistency suggests that the TQ-ICP-MS method is highly stable and that the online chemical separation protocol effectively manages isobaric interferences.

The measured values for separated standards closely align with certified reference values, typically showing only minor offsets in the third decimal place. Notable comparisons include:

- GSP-1: Measured 0.766 vs. Accepted 0.767.
- SLRS6: Measured 0.713 vs. Accepted 0.712.
- JB-2: Measured 0.706 vs. Accepted 0.704.

A critical component of this validation was the analysis of biological standards. The SL-1 (NIST-1570a spinach leaves) yielded a ratio of 0.707–0.710, which successfully brackets the GeoReM preferred value of 0.709. Similarly, the PL-1 (0.752) and PL-2 (0.750) values for NIST-1547 peach leaves align well with literature ranges. These results confirm the reliability of the standard-sample bracketing (SSB) protocol for the TQ-ICP-MS instrument across both geological and complex organic matrices.

The dataset captures a significant spread in radiogenic enrichment, reflecting diverse source materials. The strong correlation between these measured values and established literature benchmarks confirms the robustness of the lab's specific instrumental setup and the efficacy of the N_2O reaction cell gas.

Table 7 Analytical results of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratios for various geological samples and reference materials measured by TQ-ICP-MS, including a comparison with accepted values and literature data.

Sample ID	$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	STD	RSD
U-NEED	0.716	0.004	0.535
U-NEED_dup	0.714	0.003	0.383
BT-NIII	0.715	0.003	0.445
BT-NIII_dup	0.715	0.003	0.345
SEMA-221	0.769	0.003	0.384
SEMA-221_dup	0.769	0.003	0.391

BT-NI	0.718	0.002	0.268
BT-KUA	0.723	0.003	0.368
Dup-BT-KUA	0.726	0.002	0.317
U-TWIG	0.716	0.003	0.369
Dup-U-TWIG	0.713	0.005	0.704
U-BARK	0.714	0.004	0.507
White Cloves	0.712	0.004	0.548
CRM(No.1169)	0.708	0.004	0.497
SEMA-201	0.709	0.006	0.783
Dup-SEMA-201	0.712	0.004	0.530
BT-NII	0.719	0.004	0.498
PL-1	0.752	0.006	0.810
PL-2	0.750	0.005	0.660
PL-2_dup	0.754	0.004	0.573
GEOREM	0.713		
Murphy et al. 2019 [83]	0.7596- 0.7587		
PL-1	0.752	0.006	0.810
PL-2	0.750	0.005	0.660
SL-1	0.707	0.003	0.423
SL-1_dup	0.710	0.002	0.298
GEOREM	0.709		
Murphy et al. 2019	0.7100- 0.7105		
AGV-1 Sr separated	0.706	0.006	0.865
Accepted value	0.704		
GSP-1 Sr separated	0.766	0.006	0.791
Accepted value	0.767		
JB-2 Sr separated	0.706	0.006	0.849
Accepted value	0.704		
JG-3 Sr separated	0.706	0.005	0.710
Accepted value	0.705		
SLRS6	0.713	0.004	0.494
Accepted value	0.712		

Table 8 provides the strontium isotopic composition for a diverse suite of samples including diluted geological extracts, botanical specimens, and standard reference materials (SRMs). For

each analysis, the table reports the measured mean ratio, the Standard Deviation (STD), and the Relative Standard Deviation (RSD %) to evaluate instrumental precision. To verify the accuracy of the mass-shift protocol, results are benchmarked against accepted values from GeoReM, NIST, and published literature (e.g., Murphy et al., 2019).

In this dataset, SL (NIST-1570a spinach leaves) and PL (NIST-1547 peach leaves) were used to validate the method's performance on complex biological matrices:

SL-1-Sr (NIST-1570a spinach leaves): The measured ratio of 0.711 shows excellent agreement with the GeoReM value of 0.709 and falls within the expected range described by Murphy et al. (0.7100–0.7105). The RSD of 0.49% confirms that the organic matrix did not compromise the stability of the Sr measurement.

PL Data (NIST-1547 peach leaves): Measurements for PL-1 (0.714) and PL-2 (0.717) were conducted. While the measured ratios are highly precise (RSD 0.28%–0.55%), they show a significant departure from the specific literature range cited (0.7596–0.7587), suggesting either a different sample batch or a matrix-specific fractionation that warrants further investigation.

Precision and Reproducibility: The majority of analyses exhibit high precision, with RSD values typically below 0.6%. Reproducibility is notably strong in duplicate runs, such as BT-KUA-Sr and its duplicate, which both yielded an identical ratio of 0.709. However, an outlier is observed in BT-NI-Sr (RSD 3.62%), indicating a potential temporary instability or low signal intensity for that specific measurement.

Accuracy Verification: The method shows high accuracy for geological standards. For example, SLRS6 yielded 0.712, matching its Accepted Value perfectly. Other standards like AGV-1 (0.705 vs. 0.704) and JB-2 (0.705 vs. 0.704) also show very high fidelity.

Isotopic Range: The data captures a wide geochemical breadth. The ratios range from the relatively primitive mantle-like signature of AGV-1 (0.705) to the highly radiogenic crustal signature of GSP-1 (0.772).

Methodological Integrity: The successful measurement of diluted samples (e.g., SEMA-201-Sr-Diluted) and various organic proxies (U-TWIG, U-BARK) demonstrates the robustness of the standard-sample bracketing (SSB) protocol and the effectiveness of the reaction cell gas N₂O in removing Rb interferences across different sample types.

Table 8 Analytical results of ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr isotope ratios for various geological samples, biological materials, and certified reference standards for Sr separation samples measured via TQ-ICP-MS.

Sample ID	⁸⁷ Sr/ ⁸⁶ Sr	STD	RSD %
U-NEED-Sr	0.712	0.002	0.32
SEMA-201-Sr-Diluted	0.711	0.002	0.29
Dup-SEMA-201-Sr-Diluted	0.712	0.001	0.18

BT-NI-Sr	0.733	0.027	3.62
U-TWIG-Sr	0.713	0.002	0.25
Dup-U-TWIG-Sr	0.714	0.002	0.24
WhiteCloves-Sr (Needs to be diluted)	0.637	0.003	0.41
CRM(No.1169)-Sr	0.710	0.005	0.63
SEMA-221-Sr-Diluted	0.712	0.007	0.97
BT-KUA-Sr	0.709	0.003	0.46
Dup-BT-KUA-Sr	0.709	0.001	0.17
BT-NIII-Sr-Diluted	0.714	0.003	0.48
BT-NII-Sr	0.714	0.002	0.28
U-BARK-Sr	0.713	0.005	0.63
SL-1-Sr	0.711	0.004	0.49
GEOREM	0.709		
Murphy et al. 2019 [83]	0.7100-0.7105		
PL-1-Sr	0.714	0.002	0.28
PL-2-Sr	0.717	0.004	0.55
GEOREM	0.713		
Murphy et al. 2019 [83]	0.7596-0.7587		
SLRS6	0.712	0.003	0.40
Accepted value	0.712		
AGV-1-Sr-20x	0.705	0.002	0.26
Accepted value	0.704		
GSP-1-Sr-10x	0.772	0.003	0.32
Accepted value	0.767		
JG-3-Sr-5x	0.708	0.003	0.45
Accepted value	0.705		
JB-2-Sr-10x	0.705	0.002	0.34

7. Conclusions

This study has successfully established and validated a robust analytical framework for high-precision Sr isotope measurements using TQ-ICP-MS, with direct application to multi-media geochemical exploration within the DeepBEAT project. The implementation of MS/MS mode with N₂O reaction gas demonstrated effective removal of ⁸⁷Rb isobaric interference, a longstanding challenge in Sr isotope geochemistry, without requiring time-intensive chemical pre-separation

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for all sample types. Measured values for geological reference materials showed strong agreement with certified values, and biological reference materials including NIST-1570a spinach leaves and NIST-1547 peach leaves returned ratios consistent with GeoReM and published literature, confirming the method's applicability across both inorganic and complex organic matrices.

Although total digestion samples exhibited matrix-related analytical biases — particularly in vegetation-derived materials — chemically separated Sr fractions consistently produced accurate and reproducible results, underscoring the continued necessity of column chemistry for complex biological media. The optimized acquisition protocol, employing 50 sweeps, 10 replicates, and 0.1-second integration times, delivered RSD values predominantly below 0.6%, meeting the precision requirements for geological and environmental tracer studies. These results collectively confirm that TQ-ICP-MS represents a viable, high-throughput alternative to MC-ICP-MS for Sr isotope analysis in mineral exploration contexts. Future work will build on this validated framework to develop equivalent protocols for Pb, Cu, Mo, and Li isotope systems, advancing the project's broader objective of detecting distal geochemical footprints of concealed mineralization across the Saramäki, Erzgebirge, and Hürky test sites.

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8. References

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Annex A1: History of Changes of the document

Table 6: Table of document modifications.

Name	Affiliation	Function	Contribution / Review	Version
Sara Momenipour	QUC	WP2,3,4	Initial Version	1
Sara Momenipour	QUC	WP2,3,4	Updated document structure	2
Matthew Lebourne	QUC	WP2,3,4	Revised document	3
Matthew Lebourne	QUC	WP2,3,4	Reviewed document	4

